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Dr E. Charles Nelson VMM

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Tree heathers and heather trees; or advanced coalescence theory for *Erica* enthusiasts

MICHAEL D. PIRIE

Institut für Spezielle Botanik und Botanischer Garten, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität, Mainz, Germany (& Department of Biochemistry, Stellenbosch University, South Africa)

Based on work carried out in collaboration with (in alphabetical order): Dirk U. Bellstedt, Jaimé Fagúndez, Ana L. Mugrabi de Kuppler, Jens Léon and E. G. H. (Ted) Oliver

Both Ted Oliver and I have written pieces in recent issues of Heathers about the DNA project that we are involved in, using molecular methods to infer the family tree for species of *Erica* (Oliver 2011, 2014; Pirie 2012). As Ted describes in the current issue (see pp 27–34), we had the privilege last (2014) summer of being able to join a group of fellow Heather Society members on a trip to Galicia organized by Jaimé Fagúndez, and there to see many of the European species in their full glory. This trip also gave us the opportunity to talk in detail about our project, and to try to explain, with the minimum of scientific jargon, exactly what it is we are doing and why. Our “captive” audience was remarkably receptive, and suitably (in my view) appreciative of the enormous phylogenetic tree that we ceremoniously unfolded before them. Most of the actual unfolding was of African and Madagascan species. These remain the greatest challenge of our ongoing research due to both their huge numbers and close relatedness. In this article, I would like to bring you up to date on the progress that we have made with regard to the European species.

It is just two years since the publication of Charles Nelson’s beautiful and long-awaited monograph *Hardy heathers from the northern hemisphere* (HHNH; Nelson 2012), but already we have some new results from DNA analyses that can answer a few of the questions that he deliberately left open.

In his monograph, Charles organized northern *Erica* into unrepentantly artificial chapters based on overall similarity. We are warned by him in no uncertain terms not to regard this as any form of classification, and yet these are groupings of species defined by reasonable criteria that are given names – informal English ones, rather than formal botanical Latin ones – to help us remember and to talk about the plants and their characteristics. If we turn a blind eye to the denial of warranty and think about these chapters as hypotheses of relationships, one detail becomes immediately clear: of 21 species of *Erica*,

four are graced by chapters all of their own; singletons without hypothetical relationship (or even similarity) to any other species in particular. If we consider the other genera of hardy heathers, *Calluna* is a similar case. It is monotypic; a genus currently represented by just one species. The generic status tells us that *Calluna* is distinct from other members of the sub-family Ericaceae, but obviously cannot convey a sense of common attributes – there is only *Calluna vulgaris* to compare. The obvious contrast is with *Erica*, where the generic name also represents the shared characteristics of more than 800 species.

A further six chapters of HHNH treat groups of species. These present hypotheses that we can test, not just in the trivial sense of “Are these each other’s closest relatives?”, but also in terms of their shared characteristics. Is the tall habit of the “tree heathers” (*Erica arborea* and *E. lusitanica*) directly comparable? Is it shared by dint of common heritage, or did it evolve independently, perhaps in response to pressures imposed by similar habitats? Similar questions can be raised about wind pollination in the “besom heaths” (*E. scoparia*, *E. platycodon* and *E. azorica*); about flower form in the “bell heathers” (*E. cinerea*, *E. maderensis* and *E. terminalis*); and even the glandular hairs common to “cross-leaved heaths” (*E. tetralix*, *E. mackayana* and *E. andevalensis*).

And what do the molecules say? First we have to qualify the results: the molecules, insofar as we can get at them (with increasing ease, given technological advances, but still with considerable laboratory cookery) do not necessarily always speak with a united voice. We analyse DNA sequences from different chromosomes, for example; or from mitochondria or chloroplasts. The latter two are, respectively, the power stations and the photosynthesis factories of the plant cell. They are distant relatives of former free-living, single-celled, organisms and contain their own diminutive genomes that are inherited, as a rule, along the maternal line and as a single unit. This is in contrast to the paired chromosomes of the nuclear genome that are split up and passed along maternal and paternal lines separately. These, thus, are our independent genetic markers. There are various important biological phenomena that can cause these markers to show somewhat different results. I have attempted to illustrate some of these with a hypothetical species tree in Figure 1.

The most obvious such factor is hybridisation. When more or less distantly related individuals cross, the progeny can inherit chromosomes and chloroplasts implying a mixture of the phylogenetic histories of each of the two parents (Figure 1: A). Perhaps less obvious is the impact of population sizes through

Figure 1. Coalescent stochasticity, hybridization and the species tree. Hypothetical species tree of three species (X, Y and Z). The sequence and timing of speciation events is represented by the black outline that encompasses three (coloured) gene trees (1–3). The width of branches in the species tree represent relative population sizes (wider being larger). Note that although gene tree 2 shows the same branching pattern as the species tree, gene tree 1 differs due to hybridisation (grey box A) and gene tree 3 differs due to the effects of coalescent stochasticity (grey box B) given large population size in the ancestral species.

time. In short, larger populations can harbour more genetic diversity for longer than can smaller populations. At the lower extreme, very small populations result in a “genetic bottleneck”, whereby the surviving individuals are all closely related and, genetically, more or less identical. Left to chance, not all individuals will pass on their genes. In small or fragmented populations, genetic diversity can consequently decrease dramatically with each passing generation. Consider

the efforts that are made in captive breeding programmes to ensure that small “populations” of zoo animals do not become inbred. At the upper extreme, within large populations, even successful variants can be slow to spread and become the norm, whilst minority genes can persist a long time. This general phenomenon is known as “coalescent stochasticity”, meaning the random (stochastic) generation-by-generation shifting of proportions of genes (or “genotypes”) in populations. An important upshot for our purposes is that when new species originate from within large populations, individuals that we later analyse can prove to have inherited genes with phylogenetic histories that are more typical of altogether different species (Figure 1: B).

On the one hand, these factors can complicate our analyses, making it challenging to represent the species history with a phylogenetic “tree”. On the other hand, it is often exactly these phenomena that are interesting if you want to answer questions about past events: range expansions and contractions in response to climate change, for example, or where the ancestors of particular species originated. From our independent genetic markers we can infer a forest of individual “gene trees”, ideally from a number of different individuals representing the species of interest. Where the gene trees are all more or less the same, we can have confidence that this result directly represents the species tree. In such cases, we know that there will have been on average longer periods between speciation events, smaller population sizes, and less hybridisation. By the same token, when the gene trees are less harmonious we can use the degree of the differences to infer past population sizes and hybridisation events. The current theoretical challenge lies in teasing these different factors apart.

For *Erica* phylogenetics, we have so far inferred only two independent gene trees: one from the nuclear genome and a group of linked markers together representing the chloroplast genome. The phylogenetic tree presented in Figure 2 is summarized from a paper that a number of us have been working on for quite a time, but which is now finalized and currently undergoing peer review. It might not be the usual style of an article presented in *Heathers* to have multiple contributing authors, but it is in the nature of scientific research that for the larger endeavours you need to gather a critical mass of the necessary skills, experience and resources. Credit for much of the molecular work goes to Ana Kuppler, who did this as part of her doctoral thesis completed at the University of Bonn, Germany, in November 2013. Ana was helped and advised by both Jens Léon (Bonn) and Jaimé Fagúndez (Santiago de Compostela, Spain), and

Figure 2. A consensus species tree of the northern heathers, representing relationships subject to significant statistical support following the combination of two independent (chloroplast and nuclear) gene trees. Note that *Erica lusitanica* appears in two places in the tree, reflecting the different phylogenetic signals of the chloroplast and nuclear markers.

received funding from the Nordrhein-Westfalen regional government, the Faculty of Agriculture at Bonn, and the Landgard Foundation. Meanwhile, Ted Oliver, Dirk Bellstedt and I, in our work at Stellenbosch University in South Africa (myself, of late, in Mainz, Germany) have been focusing more on the larger African diversity, with funding in part from the South African National Research Foundation and the Claude Leon Foundation. Until last year our two groups were working in parallel, but we have since put our heads together to analyse our combined data and write papers.

To cut a long story short, in *Erica* our genes have generally been telling us the same story. And how does this compare to the story told in the chapters of HHNH? Pretty closely is the answer. The “cross-leaved heaths” are each other’s closest relatives, that is to say they represent a monophyletic group. So are the “besom heaths”, and so are the “winter and spring flowering heathers” (Figure 2). What does this mean for our evolutionary hypotheses? Amongst the European species there is evidence for numerous shifts in morphology but, apparently, glandular hairs evolved just once in a common ancestor of the “cross-leaved heaths”, as did wind pollination in a common ancestor of the “besom heaths”. There appears to be some “phylogenetic conservatism” – evolutionary inertia, so to speak – in flowering time too.

Other groups, such as the “bell heathers” (*Erica cinerea*, *E. maderensis* and *E. terminalis*) and “*Erica vagans* and congeners” (*E. vagans*, *E. manipuliiflora*, *E. multiflora* and *E. umbellata*), fare less well in this comparison. They do not include all of each other’s closest relatives and do include the odd interloper. These thus represent non-monophyletic groupings. For example, *E. vagans* and *E. manipuliiflora* share a more recent common ancestor with the besom heaths than they do with *E. multiflora*, while *E. umbellata* appears even more distantly related. This is not so surprising; from the wider phylogeny we know that floral morphology in *Erica* has changed a great deal, with convergence to similar forms occurring frequently (Pirie et al. 2011). In this example, the highly derived wind-pollination syndrome of the besom heaths (that is, their reduced flowers and expanded stigmas) evolved once, overwriting most other floral morphological similarities to their closest relatives.

And the singletons? *Erica ciliaris* is closely related to the cross-leaved heaths, together forming a group that are all characterised by those glandular hairs. However, even in the molecular phylogeny, the relationships of the other singletons currently remain mostly unclear, and the signs are that this may remain so. The phylogeny seems to show a rapid sequence of speciation events leading to the origins of a number of lineages including oddities such as *E. spiculifolia* and *E. sicula*. This is a common challenge for phylogenetic inference, and under such circumstances the precise order of the speciation events may have less influence on morphological characteristics than does the long subsequent divergence. In the case of *E. australis*, we have a clearer result, but this places it in splendid isolation, the single sister group to the giant African/Madagascan clade. Treating these species under their own “chapters” may not allow us to

generalize, but then again neither can it mislead us into assuming attributes in common with other groups that may be very different. The solution used in HHNH seems in retrospect a rather reasonable one.

So, our independent markers have proved generally consistent, but more rarely, they have actively disagreed. We expected differing results from *Erica* × *stuartii* (the only known hybrid that we included in the analyses), and indeed our chloroplast markers were effectively identical to those of the maternal *E. tetralix*, whilst the nuclear marker showed both *E. tetralix* and *E. mackayana* characteristics. A more surprising exception to the rule of congruent gene trees in European *Erica* is *E. lusitanica*. Our chloroplast markers tell us that *E. lusitanica* is more closely related to species such as *E. cinerea* and *E. maderensis*; the nuclear marker places it firmly with the other tree heather *E. arborea* in the “African/Madagascan” clade. With just two gene trees and this particular result it is not possible to say conclusively whether ancient hybridization or coalescent stochasticity (given large past effective population sizes) is to blame. However, the close morphological similarity of *E. lusitanica* to *E. arborea* is an indication that the chloroplast might have been “captured” following a past hybridization event. This is to argue that tall habit (and various other similarities) in the tree heathers evolved once, rather than in parallel.

Informal meetings such as ours in Galicia last summer present a fantastic opportunity to help along the kind of collaborative effort that delivered these results. As well as discussing our current work, we also looked to the future and what we might yet be able to achieve in researching European *Erica*. A good number of our current samples of European species have already been contributed by Heather Society members, to whom we are extremely grateful. So, as a final note here I would like to put out a further request on behalf of our research team: to anyone planning their holidays in heather country in the forthcoming flowering season, we would be very interested to hear from you.

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